

README.txt:

o Instrument description and calibration status

Two lidar systems were used to retrieve aerosol optical properties: the DEPOLarization lidar systEm (DEPOLE) and the elastic-Raman lidar system aErosol and Ozone Lidar system (EOLE).

DEPOLE is based on a pulsed Nd: YAG laser emitting at 355 and 532 nm with linear polarization purity more than 99.5%, achieved using a polarizing filter. The elastically backscattered lidar signals are collected at both wavelengths by a 200 mm diameter Dall-Kirkham (f/4) Cassegrainian telescope and are separated into parallel and cross-polarization components using polarizing beam splitter cubes. DEPOLE achieves full overlap at approximately 500 m a.s.l. (Papayannis et al., 2020). DEPOLE provides vertical profiles of the aerosol elastic backscatter coefficient and volume and particle linear depolarization ratios VLDR and PLDR, respectively, at 355 and 532 nm, as well as the aerosol Ångström exponent between these two wavelengths ($AE_{355/532}$). During BIOSPHERE Campaign we focused on 532 nm measurements from DEPOLE and also, aerosol mass concentration profiles for dust and non-dust components were estimated using the POLIPHON algorithm (Ansmann et al., 2012; Mamouri and Ansmann, 2014; Tesche et al., 2009), which combines depolarization lidar and sun photometer data. Depolarization lidar distinguishes dust from non-dust aerosols from aerosol backscatter and depolarization profiles, while sun photometry provides fine/coarse-mode AODs and microphysical properties (volume and surface area). Mass concentrations were calculated using aerosol-specific properties like PLDR, lidar ratio, density, and volume-to-AOD ratios. To this end we used a coarse-mode density of 2.6 g cm^{-3} (dust) (Hess et al., 1998; Proestakis et al., 2024) and a fine-mode density of 1.35 g/cm^{-3} (smoke) (Engelhart et al., 2012; Reid et al., 2005). The method remains effective even when lidar and photometer data are not strictly collocated, especially for stable dust events. Total uncertainty in retrieved mass concentrations is $\sim 36\text{-}40\%$ and assumed mass densities ($\pm 20\%$). Volume-to-AOD ratios may vary by up to 10% for dust and 20% for smoke (Ansmann et al., 2012, 2019).

The **EOLE** lidar system is based on a pulsed Nd: YAG laser emitting simultaneously at 355, 532, and 1064 nm. The receiving unit includes a 300 mm diameter (f/2) Cassegrainian telescope, which collects both the elastically backscattered signals and the vibrational-rotational Raman signals generated by atmospheric N_2 at 387 and 607 nm, and H_2O at 407 nm. EOLE provides vertical profiles of the aerosol backscatter coefficients at 355, 532, and 1064 nm, and extinction coefficients at 355 and 532 nm, as well as the water vapor mixing ratio in the troposphere. Additionally, EOLE provides vertical profiles of intensive aerosol parameters, including the lidar ratio (LR) at 355 and 532 nm, and aerosol Ångström exponents derived from extinction ($AE_{e355/532}$) and backscatter ($AE_{b355/532}$, $AE_{b532/1064}$) coefficients. The system reaches full overlap at approximately 800 m a.s.l.. Based on these observations and using well-known methodologies, we can separate the lidar signals between aerosols and clouds, spherical and non-spherical particles in mixed aerosol layers (Ansmann et al., 2012, 2019; Tesche et al., 2009).

EOLE (1) and DEPOLE (3) lidar systems along with their telescopes (2 and 4, respectively) are presented in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. EOLE (1) and DEPOLE (3) lidar systems along with their telescopes (2 and 4, respectively) in the Laser Remote Sensing Unit (LRSU) in the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

o Calibration status

The last calibration of the DEPOLE lidar system was performed on 17 July 2023, while the EOLE lidar was calibrated on 17 August 2023, during the campaign. A subsequent calibration was carried out for EOLE on 15 November 2023, following the [QA/QC calibration standards](#) of ACTRIS – Center for Aerosol Remote Sensing.

Prior to the campaign, both lidar systems had been calibrated on 10 November 2022.

o Measurement period and time standard

The measurement period extends from 1 June 2023 till 30 August 2023.

Each **Level 2** file, which contains the non-smoothed lidar data, is name as:

atyyyymmdd_starttime_stoptime_lv2.nc

(e.g. at20230601_1843_1935_lv2.nc)

Similarly, each **Level 3**, which contains the smoothed lidar data, follows the format:

atyyyymmdd_starttime_stoptime_lv3.nc

(e.g. at20230601_1843_1935_lv3.nc)

o Column names and units

Both Level 2 and Level 3 .nc files follow a specific format with standardized column names and units, as described below:

-DEPOLE Lidar System – Depolarization Variable

Variable	Description	Units
Height_amsl	Height above mean sea level	m
Backscatter_532_dust	Dust backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532_non_dust	Non-dust backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532_total	Total backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Dust_mass_concentration	Dust mass concentration	$\mu g m^{-3}$
Non_dust_mass_concentration	Non-dust mass concentration	$\mu g m^{-3}$
Mass_concentration_total	Total mass concentration	$\mu g m^{-3}$
PLDR_532	Particle Linear Depolarization Ratio at 532 nm	dimensionless

-EOLE Lidar System

Variable	Description	Units
Angstroem_backscatter_355_1064	Ångström exponent (backscatter 355/1064 nm)	–
Angstroem_backscatter_355_532	Ångström exponent (backscatter 355/532 nm)	–
Angstroem_backscatter_532_1064	Ångström exponent (backscatter 532/1064 nm)	–
Angstroem_extinction_355_1064	Ångström exponent (extinction 355/1064 nm)	–
Atmospheric_density	Atmospheric density	cm^{-3}
Backscatter_1064	Backscatter at 1064 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532	Backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_355	Backscatter at 355 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532_dust	Dust backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532_non_dust	Non-dust backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Backscatter_532_total	Total backscatter at 532 nm	$Mm^{-1} sr^{-1}$
Extinction_355	Extinction at 355 nm	Mm^{-1}
Extinction_532	Extinction at 532 nm	Mm^{-1}
Height_amsl_(b1064)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for backscatter at 1064 nm	m
Height_amsl_(b532)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for backscatter at 532 nm	m
Height_amsl_(b355)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for backscatter at 355 nm	m
Height_amsl_(e532)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for extinction at 532 nm	m
Height_amsl_(e355)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for extinction at 355 nm	m

Height_amsl_(density)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for atmospheric density	m
Height_amsl_(LR,Angstroem)	Height (a.m.s.l.) for Lidar Ratio and Ångström exponent	m
LidarRatio_355	Lidar ratio at 355 nm	sr
LidarRatio_532	Lidar ratio at 532 nm	sr
Dust_mass_concentration	Dust mass concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
Non_dust_mass_concentration	Non-dust mass concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
Mass_concentration_total	Total mass concentration	$\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$
PLDR_532	Particle Linear Depolarization Ratio at 532 nm	dimensionless

o Contact person (name, email, institute)

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References

Ansmann, A., Seifert, P., Tesche, M., and Wandinger, U.: Profiling of fine and coarse particle mass: case studies of Saharan dust and Eyjafjallajökull/Grimsvötn volcanic plumes, *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, **12**, 9399–9415, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-12-9399-2012>, 2012.

Ansmann, A., Mamouri, R.-E., Hofer, J., Baars, H., Althausen, D., and Abdullaev, S. F.: Dust mass, cloud condensation nuclei, and ice-nucleating particle profiling with polarization lidar: updated POLIPHON conversion factors from global AERONET analysis, *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, **12**, 4849–4865, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-4849-2019>, 2019.

Engelhart, G. J., Hennigan, C. J., Miracolo, M. A., Robinson, A. L., and Pandis, S. N.: Cloud condensation nuclei activity of fresh primary and aged biomass burning aerosol, *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, **12**, 7285–7293, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-12-7285-2012>, 2012.

Hess, M., Koepke, P., and Schult, I.: Optical Properties of Aerosols and Clouds: The Software Package OPAC, *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.*, **79**, 831–844, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(1998\)079%253C0831:OPOAAC%253E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1998)079%253C0831:OPOAAC%253E2.0.CO;2), 1998.

Mamouri, R. E. and Ansmann, A.: Fine and coarse dust separation with polarization lidar, *Atmospheric Meas. Tech.*, **7**, 3717–3735, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-7-3717-2014>, 2014.

Papayannis, A., Kokkalis, P., Mylonaki, M., Soupiona, R., Papanikolaou, C. A., Foskinis, R., and Giakoumaki, A.: Recent Upgrades of the EOLE and AIAS Lidar Systems of the National Technical University of Athens Operating Since 2000 in Athens, Greece, *EPJ Web Conf.*, **237**, 02030, <https://doi.org/10.1051/epjconf/202023702030>, 2020.

Proestakis, E., Gkikas, A., Georgiou, T., Kampouri, A., Drakaki, E., Ryder, C., Marengo, F., Marinou, E., and Amiridis, V.: A near-global multiyear climate data record of the fine-mode and coarse-mode components of atmospheric pure-dust, *Aerosols/Remote Sensing/Data Processing and Information Retrieval*, <https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-2023-262>, 2024.

Reid, J. S., Eck, T. F., Christopher, S. A., Koppmann, R., Dubovik, O., Eleuterio, D. P., Holben, B. N., Reid, E. A., and Zhang, J.: A review of biomass burning emissions part III: intensive optical properties of biomass burning particles, *Atmospheric Chem. Phys.*, 5, 827–849, <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-5-827-2005>, 2005.

Tesche, M., Ansmann, A., Müller, D., Althausen, D., Engelmann, R., Freudenthaler, V., and Groß, S.: Vertically resolved separation of dust and smoke over Cape Verde using multiwavelength Raman and polarization lidars during Saharan Mineral Dust Experiment 2008, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmospheres*, 114, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009JD011862>, 2009.